

MOTIVATION OF LEVEL ONE AND TWO STUDENTS' ON CPFS IN THE OFFLINE MODE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6369112>

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Аннотация: *В статье обсуждается фактор мотивации в формате оффлайн-обучения на примере курса Доуниверситетской подготовки МВУТ.*

Ключевые слова: *Мотивация, внешняя, внутренняя.*

Annotation: *The article discusses the factor of motivation in the offline learning, using the example of WIUT Pre-university Course.*

Keywords: *Motivation, intrinsic, extrinsic.*

Abstract : This study is both empirical and descriptive in nature. Literature review, observation, questionnaire, and suggestions will all be used in the development of this report. The information that will be utilized in the study has been gathered at the first and second levels of abstraction. When it comes to the observation, a number of colleagues are part in the process, and they have all been questioned at the conclusion of the school year. There will be two variables in this investigation. There are two types of these: dependent and independent. Due to the fact that the study subject "The influence of motivation on Level One and Two Students' Performance" is connected to the field of social science, it is not possible to quantify these factors. The experimenters are searching for any conceivable influence on the dependent variable that may be induced by altering the independent variable in order to complete the experiment. It is based on the analysis of cause and effect linkages of elements that contribute to internal and extrinsic motivation, to put it another way. Introduction and background

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Introduction and background

Literature review

Modern western education is predicated mostly on the ideals of self-direction and self-regulation. Since young people are already at an age when they may be held accountable for their choices about their education. According to Knowles, students enter higher education with a greater sense of purpose and are highly motivated (1975). Despite this, there is some indication that students take less effort to engage in

numerous extracurricular events that are arranged by the university administration for their convenience and betterment than in previous years. A particular concentration of this tendency may be seen at educational facilities. What impact may it have on one's autonomy? This article will look at several ideas of motivation and autonomy from a variety of perspectives. It will also explore how different variables may have an impact on them. The article will include recommendations for policies and procedures that may be implemented to promote student autonomy in higher education.

Learner autonomy is commonly misunderstood to mean 'simply sitting at home and studying alone' (Dixon, 2006). In spite of this, the Columbia Electronic Encyclopedia asserts that autonomy has political origins, and that it refers to "self-rule of the state." As a result, in education, autonomy is defined as the ability of pupils to make choices, including the ability to set personal goals for themselves (Little, 1991: p. 14; Holec, 1985: p. 180). Furthermore, according to Voller (1997), the instructor's position in learner autonomy is not overlooked; the teacher engages with students as a facilitator, or in the case of face-to-face tutorials, the role is referred to as a counselor, when appropriate. Deci and Ryan hypothesize that there is a relationship between autonomy and motivation (1985: p. 35). They distinguish between two forms of motivation: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Students who are intrinsically driven accomplish the assignment because they have a personal desire and interest, as opposed to students who are extrinsically motivated, who finish the task as a result of external circumstances such as a reward or penalty. The researchers may reasonably conclude that learner autonomy is inextricably linked to intrinsic motivation since intrinsic motivation is defined as the desire to accept responsibility, while learner autonomy is defined as the act of accepting responsibility. Students in education, according to Deci and Ryan (1985: p. 355), do not generally have a strong enough desire to learn something that is both required and uninteresting to them, according to Deci and Ryan. It is proposed that certain extrinsic devices should be used in order to generate intrinsic motivation at an earlier level. Students from levels one and two at the Westminster International University in Tashkent will be encouraged to engage in extracurricular activities, as will be shown in a number of case studies.

Current research and analysis

The Basics of English for Academic Purposes module featured a number of club activities that were designed to help students improve their speaking, writing, and reading abilities. The average age of level 1 pupils is from 15 to 21 years old. The bulk of pupils, on the other hand, are between the ages of 16 and 18. All of them had come from a different learning environment, where they were compelled to study and achieve better than they otherwise would. In this particular instance, they were either reprimanded or awarded with school credits. Despite this, the academic atmosphere does not imply any kind of coercion. It is vital to acknowledge that the Western system of education is very different from the one that is taught in schools today. A good transition from a high

school to a university setting is essential for students' future success. It is difficult to expect pupils to be completely self-sufficient in the absence of any precondition. As a result, it was not originally agreed to make attendance at Student Support Sessions, which were hosted in a virtual environment, mandatory. Eventually, the attendance metrics showed a very high level of participation. Only a small fraction of level 1 students, around 3 percent out of a total of 100 percent, failed to try many sessions due to a variety of reasons. According to the questionnaire, which was issued to level 1 students at the conclusion of the 2013-2014 academic year, it was clear that they were enthusiastic about all of the activities and indicated a desire to engage in the same sessions at the next academic level in the future. Some of them, on the other hand, requested that they be evaluated based on their participation and attendance in these events. Therefore, upon revalidation, participation and homework get a 10% weighting in the total grade distribution. Students' engagement should be rewarded, as previously indicated, since this is an indicator of extrinsic motivation. It seems that a year is insufficient time for both instructors and level 1 students to acquire autonomy, since extrinsic motivation continues to play a significant role in students' capacity to make choices that are connected to their academic work.

We chose to watch a group of around 250 level 2 students in order to investigate the differences in the influence of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on the students of Basics of Quantities Skills. We analyzed their responses and involvement in various kinds of activities. Aside from that, their general behavioral patterns were observed in order to determine if extrinsic incentive may have a good impact on their involvement and attendance.

In particular, CPFS students were first assigned home projects for independent practice, which, however, did not appear on their performance records. This was particularly beneficial for genuinely driven kids, who either found joy in tackling Math problems or recognized the importance of homework in their overall growth. However, as compared to the ratio of students who submitted their homework activities following the modifications in assessment, the proportion of students who made an all-out effort to do their best when completing their homework was much lower (about 40 percent). It was then decided that the homework given to each subject would be incorporated as an evaluation component, with students receiving genuine grades that would have an impact on their overall performance during the school year. The significant thing to note here is that after adding homework to the assessment components, the percentage of students who submitted their responses increased considerably, reaching almost 100 percent. Actually, this instance demonstrates that intrinsic drive does not have the same impact on teens as extrinsic motivation has on them.

Another observation that leads to the same conclusions is the participation in math competitions, which is another example. In previous years, it had been agreed to arrange a local championship among CPFS students to encourage them to participate. Due to

the fact that the event was conducted during class, the attendance rate was high; nonetheless, the attitude of many students indicated that they were either uninterested or completely disinterested in the conclusion of the tournament. A large number of questions were raised about the impending exam by students, with the majority of them wanting to know if any of the contest issues were comparable to those on the test. Consequently, it seems that younger students place more importance on their grades than they do on their real comprehension of the topic, which might have been determined by their performance in the competition.

Aside from that, the case study was undertaken in order to determine whether or not the pupils were present. Because students had a tendency to skip certain courses throughout a semester, and because the university policy had been amended to impose a greater check on attendance, this was reflected in the CPFS as well as other places. The substantial drop in absence rates that has been noticed over the previous couple of years may be attributed to the implementation of the new attendance record system. In the event of a student's absence from class for two or more consecutive sessions, the registrar's office notifies his or her parents immediately, and the student is required to complete a specific form with an explanation of their absence. In addition, students are notified at the start of the academic year that repeated absences may result in severe disciplinary action being taken against them. Typically, a student who skips more than 25 percent of the sessions will be penalized with a lower grade for participation in the class. In other cases, the student may even be dismissed from the course. Such a negative attitude about absence and treating it as a kind of misbehavior had a negative impact on the absence rate, which also indicates the efficiency of extrinsic motivation, which occurs when pupils are motivated to do something in order to avoid a punishment or consequence.

Finally, conclusions and recommendations are provided.

The findings of our observation are similar with the findings of the literature study, indicating that students are more driven by external criteria such as grades and academic achievement than by internal elements such as motivation. Their behavioral patterns indicate that they are concerned about punishments and scores. This, however, does not imply that intrinsic drive has no influence on students at all; rather, it suggests that extrinsic incentive would more effectively increase students' engagement.

Students, on the other hand, are most likely aware of the English language skill gaps they have, if not by their own observation, then from the feedback they get from instructors. The most important thing to do now is to fix the situation. The most difficult element is convincing oneself that professional assistance is necessary. According to what I've seen when teaching, learners are mostly driven extrinsically to achieve their goals. For example, a student submits a coursework only if it is one of the module components, and the degree classification is determined by the total grade

achieved by the module component in the following chain. Students usually want some kind of motivation to complete a task, whether it is a grade, a certificate, or the opportunity to get their ideal career, which is strongly tied to the education they obtain. As a result, it is vital to consider ways of inspiring pupils, even though it first appeared unusual to urge individuals to seek any kind of assistance.

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